

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

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PEER REVIEW TO IMPROVE A CULTURE OF SAFETY:
A QUALITY IMPROVEMENT PROJECT

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

A Medical Incident (MI) is defined as a preventable or a near-miss medical event that can lead to patient harm. An estimated 251,454 patients per year are involved in MIs, and one in three healthcare workers will be involved in a MI during their career. Research suggests that promoting a culture of safety improves MI reporting. When MIs are reported, efforts can be made to prevent their reoccurrence. A culture of safety is defined as a pervasive attitude throughout an organization to mitigate the occurrence of adverse events (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2019.a). Existing evidence suggests that an incident-based peer review (IBPR) process improves perceptions of a culture of safety and reporting of MIs. IBPR is a standardized process that involves nurses identifying contributing factors when a MI occurs. Thus, the purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to improve the reporting of MIs by promoting a culture of safety through the development, implementation, and evaluation of an incidence-based peer review (IBPR) process in an acute care urban facility.

The Model for Improvement provided the conceptual foundation for this quality improvement project. Three RNs from separate medical-surgical units identified system causes of MIs in weekly IBPR meetings. Staff received feedback from IBPR meetings and MI counts were tracked weekly. Changes in the culture of safety were measured by the adapted AHRQ Survey on Patient Safety Culture™ (AHRQ-SOPS™). System causes of MIs were counted from each IBPR meeting. The call light response time (CLRT) was used

to measure the impact of staff attending the IBPR meetings on the unit's ability to answer call lights in a prompt manner. Nurses provided evaluations of the IBPR process.

The overall results of the IBPR, while generally positive, were mixed. The reporting of MIs did not increase over the course of this project, in fact it decreased. Seven of the eight adapted-AHRQ-SOPSTM items reflected improvement. IBPR did not negatively impact CLRT and nurse evaluations of the process were positive.

Data suggest the culture of safety generally improved through the IBPR process. MI reporting may have decreased for several reasons. MI baseline data was collected when new interns and residents began their training, possibly inflating the true number of MIs. Additionally, MIs may have decreased because of increased sensitivity to MIs and improvements in nursing practice.

Limitations warrant caution in the interpretation and application of these results due to the fact that the author was present at the IBPR meetings, which may have led the nurses to evaluate the IBPR favorably. In addition, the use of Likert scales may have potentially contributed to a common response bias which is an identified error as evidenced by the fact that several staff scored the survey with the same response for all eight questions. As a result, the interpretation and application of these results should be done cautiously. This project demonstrates the feasibility and value of implementing an IBPR process in an acute care setting. Continued management commitment to IBPR may improve the process of IBPR and staff perceptions of safety.

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BACKGROUND

Twenty years ago, in 1999, the Institute of Medicine released its report, *To Err is Human: Building a Safer Health System*, which stated that 98,000 patients die each year from medical incidents (MIs). More recent estimates suggest that the number of MIs may be closer to 251,454 patients per year, and that one in three healthcare workers will be involved in a MI during their career (Mira et al., 2015). For this project, a MI is defined as either a preventable or a near-miss medical event. The difference between a preventable and near-miss event is the outcome. Near-miss events are caught before the patient is adversely affected (Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality [AHRQ], 2019.a) while a preventable event reached the patient.

Medical incidents may result from organizational structure or process issues. Structural issues reflect institutional designs that influence safe care delivery processes while process issues are usually defects in the steps taken to complete tasks. Since registered nurses (RNs) are primarily responsible for the provision of direct care in most hospitals, they typically serve as a final barrier in preventing patient harm (Castel, Ginsburg, Zaheer, & Tamim, 2015; Rutledge, Retrosi, & Ostrowski, 2018). To learn from actual or potential MIs and to clearly identify the structure and process issues that may have contributed to an incident, the nurse needs to feel comfortable in fully disclosing and reporting an MI when it occurs.

For the nurse to feel comfortable in reporting MIs, there must be a culture of safety. A culture of safety includes all levels of an organization from staff to upper management committed to preventing MIs (AHRQ, 2019.b). Involving staff in safety rather than blaming them when MIs occur can improve the culture of safety for the

organization. Between 2007 and 2009, MIs cost the Center for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) \$7.3 billion (AHRQ, 2014). In response, and to incentivize reduction in MI rates, the CMS identified specific types of incidents, mistakes, and hospital-acquired conditions for which they would withhold reimbursement should they occur. These incidents are commonly known as *never* events due to their seriousness and the fact that they should never happen. There are currently 29 never events, which are classified by CMS into seven categories (National Quality Forum, n.d.). The list of never events continues to lengthen as the healthcare system strives to improve patient safety. These incidents, depending on their severity, may also require reporting to the California Department of Public Health or other regulatory and/or accreditation agencies where they are investigated and, if severe, may trigger an extensive review of the hospital's overall operations.

Never events are the most severe types of incidents that occur, but they are not the most common. There are any number of adverse events that may cause a patient to experience physical harm due to a clinical error (AHRQ, 2019.a). In addition to including preventable and near-miss events, adverse events were also addressed under the definition of MI for this project. In the United States, a large percentage of MIs relate to errors involving the administration of medication (AHRQ, 2019.a). Medication administration error rates are estimated to be 8% to 25% per 1,000 pharmaceutical administrations (AHRQ, 2019.a).

Fears of negative personal or career repercussions or being viewed as incompetent are disincentives to reporting (Castel et al., 2015). Hewitt, Chreim, and Forster (2017) found that nurses fear that reporting an error decreases their possibility of promotion

because they may be perceived as incompetent. Additionally, lack of feedback after reporting an incident in electronic reporting systems disincentivizes staff from reporting (Gong, Hsing-Yin, Xinshuo, & Lei, 2015).

There are two MI reporting methods which typically occur within medical facilities: self- and peer-reporting. Self-reporting is the process whereby the nurse involved completes a report describing the incident and peer-reporting is a similar process where one of the nurse's peers completes a report. Both self- and peer-reports allow for anonymity, but there is reluctance to either self- or peer-report due to concerns about punitive employer and/or peer reactions. The reality is that, without MI reporting, many MIs are not discovered and, consequently, corrective actions cannot be undertaken to prevent future error occurrences.

Problem Statement

In the United States, a large percentage of MIs relate to errors involving the administration of medication (AHRQ, 2019.a). Medication administration error rates are estimated to be 8% to 25% per 1,000 pharmaceutical administrations (AHRQ, 2019.a). In the facility chosen for this project, the medication administration error rates have been identified at 8.3% per 1,000 administrations, at the low end of the national average. A 2019 Press-Ganey nursing satisfaction survey at the project facility demonstrated that 53% of the registered nursing staff believed that the facility responded in a punitive manner when MIs associated with medication errors were reported. This finding has significance in that punitive reactions to the reporting of such errors discourages nurses from reporting at all (Castel et al., 2015).

An incident-based peer review (IBPR) program has demonstrated effectiveness in increasing both self and peer error reporting (Herrington & Hand, 2018). The IBPR process engages the involved nurse's peers in systematically reviewing the details of the MI. Nurses identify contributing factors that led to the MI and focus on identifying structural and process systems that may have triggered the MI and not on the nurse who reported it. IBPR helps nurses learn from the error by uncovering the factors that led to it, which facilitates identification of changes needed in the care delivery process and/or institutional policy changes. The IBPR process also builds trust in and facilitates the achievement of a *just culture* within the organization since the focus is on overall organizational improvement rather than assigning blame.

There are currently no IBPR processes used at the facility selected for the project. Further, a review of the records at the institution showed that the frequency of medication error reporting is decreasing, though it is unclear if this decrease is caused by an actual decrease in MIs or if it reflects a culture of fear of reporting. In discussion with administration it was decided to use an IBPR as an adjunct to reporting MIs

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project was to improve the reporting of MIs by promoting a culture of safety through the development, implementation, and evaluation of an IBPR process in an acute care urban facility.

The objectives of the project were to:

- Improve the reporting of MIs on three adult medical/surgical units over a two month-period (October 2019 to December 2019) and staff perceptions of a safe culture

- Develop and implement an IBPR process over a 2-month period (October-November 2019)
- Evaluate the influence of IBPR on the process on MI reporting and perceptions of a safe culture
- Evaluate the impact on the unit covering patients for the staff attending the IBPR

Supporting Framework

The *Model for Improvement* developed by the Associates in Process Improvement (API, n.d.) was utilized as the framework supporting this quality improvement project. The Model for Improvement is a popular framework used in healthcare to guide practice changes, facilitate rapid cycle improvement, and encourage the identification of multiple options for practice improvement. It is comprised of two separate but interrelated components that pose three fundamental quality improvement questions which lead to and support utilizing the Plan-Do-Study-Act Model (PDSA) to structure the improvement intervention (Appendix A). Three fundamental questions assist in providing focus for the quality improvement team (Institute for Healthcare Improvement [IHI], n.d.a):

- What are we trying to improve?
- How can we measure that a change occurred?
- What intervention can achieve an improvement?

For purposes of this project, the first question (“What are we trying to improve?”) assisted in bringing clarity to the overall project aim, which is to improve the reporting of MIs by promoting a culture of safety using an IBPR. Addressing the first question

assisted in clearly addressing four key implementation questions: (a) what, (b) who, (c) how much, and (d) by when (National Institute for Children's Health Quality, n.d.).

To answer the second question ("How can we measure that a change has occurred?"), nurses were surveyed as to their perceptions of the safety culture using an adapted version of the AHRQ Hospital Survey on Patient Safety Culture™ (AHRQ-SOPS™). Baseline data were collected before the implementation of the IBPR and after the intervention had been completed. The third question, ("What intervention can achieve the improvement?") was addressed by implementing the IBPR.

The second component of the Model of Improvement is the PDSA model. The PDSA model is a process for change represented by a wheel with four steps. The PDSA model involves a process of cycles that continues until the change has been accepted or rejected. AHRQ (2015) suggests that PDSA cycles should be rapid, so time is optimized.

The first step of the PDSA cycle ("PLAN") involves structuring the intervention. This planning step includes identifying how the outcome will be measured as well as the steps that must be taken to implement the intervention (Langley, 2009). Assembling a team is the first step in the planning process. The project team included members who have knowledge of nursing care processes. The team worked out the fine points of running the PDSA cycle and developed an event selection criterion. The team also designed the forms to utilize during the peer review.

Roberts and Cronin (2017) stated that conducting a root cause analysis (RCA) is an effective way for investigating MIs. Participants in the IBPR received training in the use of RCA tools. Specifically, the team was taught to use the Ishikawa diagram and utilize the Five Whys to analyze MIs. The *Ishikawa* diagram starts with a problem to be

solved. The diagram then adds broad categories such as staff, material, and methods. After the broad categories are listed, all the possible causes that could lead to the problem are listed. The 5 *Whys* starts with a problem and then ask why it occurred. When the answer is given, why is again asked. This process continues to drill down until a possible cause is found. The team also discussed the concepts of *just culture* and *second victim syndrome* to ensure the IBPR focused on system defects and not on placing blame on the person who committed the MI.

The “DO” step of the PDSA cycle involved the selection of a MI that occurred on one of the inpatient units and the implementation of the IBPR. The members of the peer-review process (three non-supervisory nurses) used the RCA tools to identify the factors that contributed to the MI. Data collected included the outcome of the RCA, how the IBPR process was perceived by those involved, and the number of weekly MIs.

The third step of the PDSA cycle was the “STUDY” of the data collected. In this step, the team examined the results of the surveys to see if there were improvements in the perceptions of just culture and safety and reporting of MIs (Langley, 2009). Lessons learned during the implementation were discussed as a team. Evaluating the lessons learned drove the fourth step of the PDSA cycle, which addresses what to do next. The “ACT” step is the fourth part of the PDSA cycle. For this step, findings from the study phase determined whether to abandon the change, adapt the change, or adopt the change (Carnegie Foundation, n.d.). Abandoning the change would occur when no refinements to the intervention were likely to result in the desired outcome. However, no PDSA cycles are failures. Even abandoning an intervention teaches participants what does not work. The practice change can be adapted or adopted in this stage. Efforts to

sustain the practice change may include scheduled monitoring or reinforcement of the program (IHI, 2017).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A review of the literature was conducted utilizing the databases CINAHL, Google Scholar, One Search, Ovid, and PubMed. Initial search terms were Just Culture, safety culture, peer review, second victim, and reporting of incidents. Following the initial search, additional search terms were added including peer-to-peer review, adverse events, report of the incident, feedback, and nursing. Searches were filtered to limit the search to peer-reviewed journals published in the English language between 2014 and 2019. Additional literature was reviewed if identified as salient to the topics of interest. Publications excluded from the search were peer reviews for teaching and peer reviews of research studies. A table of evidence was created categorizing studies under the following subtopics: culture of safety, peer review, reporting of incidents, and second victim.

Reporting of Incidents

Medical incidents (MIs) are a major concern in healthcare. According to Farag, Blegen, Gedney-Lose, Lose, and Perkhounkova (2017), MIs are the third leading cause of deaths in the United States. The Joint Commission requires reporting of MIs, and reporting is a valuable tool for learning and corrective actions (Hewitt et al., 2017). Voluntary reporting is the most common method of reporting MIs (Farag et al., 2017; Hewitt et al., 2017). Castel et al. (2015) found that nursing staff are the most frequent self- or peer-reporters of MIs. Unfortunately, underreporting of MIs by both individuals involved in MIs and peers is a major concern (Castel et al., 2015; Hewitt et al., 2017).

There are many barriers that contribute to underreporting of MIs. Complicated forms that require multiple fields of information provide frustration (Mirbaha, Shalviri, Yazdizadeh, Gholami, & Majdzadeh, 2015). The RNs' frustration increases when they are

delayed in completing their shift assignments due to the need to complete a MI report (Mirbaha et al., 2015). Other barriers include perceptions that errors are inevitable and the lack of feedback to the reporting party (Hewitt et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2019).

Not only can the actual process of reporting MIs discourage reporting, researchers have identified fears of repercussions and fears of perceptions of incompetence as contributing factors that inhibit reporting (Castel et al., 2015). Repercussions from managers can take many forms. The manager can make nurses feel incompetent by belittling them in front of other staff or assigning them to fewer challenging patients. The manager may reprimand or suspend nurses for making errors, making them feel unsure of their skills and worried about both their employment and their future as nurses (Mirbaha et al., 2015).

In a near-miss incident, lack of harm to the patient was found to be a reason to not report (Castel et al., 2015; Farag et al., 2017). If the MI is a near-miss and no harm occurred, the nurse may find it easier to simply fix the problem rather than report it (Farag et al., 2017). The nurse may perceive lack of teamwork or managerial support as reasons not to complete a MI report (David, 2018; Mirbaha et al., 2015). The outcomes of a MI do not end with the report submission for the nurse involved, they may have to overcome the effects of Second Victim Syndrome (SVS).

Second Victim Syndrome

An often-neglected part of MI reporting is the SVS. The second victim is defined as a healthcare provider who is involved in a patient safety event (Wu, 2000). Wu described the experience stating, “Virtually every practitioner knows the sickening realization of making a bad mistake. You feel singled out and exposed.... You agonize

about what to do....Later, the event replays itself over and over in your mind” (Wu, 2000, p. 726). Some nurses can commit an error, learn from it, and move on. Other nurses cannot let the event go and they become a second victim. The second victim feels distressed, anxious, guilty, embarrassed, and traumatized after discovering that they committed a MI (Joesten, Cipparrone, Okuno-Jones, & DuBose, 2015; Mira et al., 2015).

Edrees et al. (2016) found that not addressing second victim issues could lead to further difficulties for nurses. If nurses continue to struggle with the MI, they enter the stage of guilt internalization in which they struggle with sleep deprivation, irritability, and trouble focusing on tasks (Wijaya, Mohamad, & Hafzzurachman, 2018). If second victims do not improve, they advance to the next stage of SVS (Wijaya et al., 2018). In this stage, the nurses’ personalities may change, and eventually, they develop post-traumatic stress syndrome that can last decades (Wijaya et al., 2018).

Mira et al. (2015) reported that one in three healthcare workers are involved in a MI during their career. Van Gerven et al. (2016) found that the greater the harm to the patient, the more distress experienced by the nurse. Scott et al. (2009) discussed the six stages of healing after a MI. The stages in order are chaos and accident response, intrusive reflections, restoring personal integrity, enduring the inquisition, obtaining emotional first aid, and moving on (Scott et al., 2009). Therefore, empathic communication with the nurse involved is important (Mira et al., 2015) and decreases the psychological impact of the MI (Van Gerven et al., 2016).

Research suggests that improving the culture of safety could prevent the negative effects found among second victims (Burlison et al., 2016; Wijaya et al., 2018). Van Gerven et al. (2016) found that non-punitive actions decrease the risk of psychological

distress. By improving the culture of safety, the risk of nurses developing SVS may decrease. The Joint Commission (TJC, 2017) defines a culture of safety as the sum of an organization's beliefs, perceptions, and commitments (both by collectively and individually) to quality and patient safety.

Peer Review

Peer review is a tool approach that involves peers reviewing a nurse's performance (Herrington & Hand, 2018; LeClair-Smith et al., 2016). Reviewing staff performance helps to uncover process problems and improve patient safety and does not focus on punitive actions (Herrington & Hand, 2018; LeClair-Smith et al., 2016; Roberts & Cronin, 2017). According to Fox, Bump, Butler, Chen, and Buchert (2017), participating in improving the safety culture leads to an increase in MI reporting in their study of pediatric residents.

Whitney, Haag-Heitman, Chisholm, and Gale (2016) stated that performance evaluation, clinical reviews, and IBPR are all types of peer review. An IBPR refers to a group of peers identifying gaps in the process and suggesting corrective actions for a MI (Whitney et al., 2016). In addition, Roberts and Cronin (2017) found that peer review is useful for reviewing MIs.

There are barriers to implementing peer reviews. Staff may feel discomfort with the process of evaluating others. Barriers to peer review include discomfort, lack of communication skills, retaliation, bullying, dishonesty, and the perception that it is not a role for a non-supervising nurse (LeClair-Smith et al., 2016). Hurtado et al. (2017) stated that improving the safety culture of an organization improves the job satisfaction of the nurse that, in turn, improves the nurse's performance.

As noted by Roberts and Cronin (2017) in their descriptive study of nursing peer review programs, it appears that peer review processes are not consistent. LeClair-Smith et al. (2016) found that teaching nurses how to communicate feedback is important. However, this literature review found little discussion on techniques to use during the peer review process.

Summary

The literature reviewed showed that a culture of safety improves MI reporting and decreases SVS (Burlison et al., 2016; Castel et al., 2015; Wijaya et al., 2018). In addition, nonpunitive peer review involves nursing staff reviewing MIs for system failures before placing blame on the nurses involved in the MIs. Feedback from the peer review and nonpunitive review of each MI can improve the culture of safety and decrease the risk for SVS (Burlison et al., 2016; Van Gerven et al., 2016; Wijaya et al., 2018)

METHODS

A quality improvement (QI) project was developed to promote a just culture surrounding MIs and foster a culture of safety in the author's practice setting. QI is a systematic approach at changing and measuring process outcomes. This section describes the design, setting, sample, stakeholders, ethical considerations, procedures, measures, and data analysis used in this project.

Design

The API Model for Improvement was utilized to change the culture of safety using peer review to improve MI reporting at an urban facility. The API model facilitated small rapid changes with dedicated staff involvement, which is the most common QI approach in health care (AHRQ, 2013).

Setting

The project setting was an acute care, academic facility located in a large urban center in Southern California. An electronic reporting program was utilized to report MIs. The reporting program is anonymous but includes fields to enter the names of patients and staff involved if known.

Sample

The sample population for the AHRQ-SOPS™ included a convenience sample of RNs from three adult medical/surgical units. RNs in supervisory positions were excluded from this project. Eighty-eight RNs completed the pre-adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ related to perceptions of a safety culture (Appendix B). A subset of these RNs ($n=25$) completed an evaluation of the IBPR (Appendix C). There were 121 RNs who completed the same adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ after the intervention. The MIs for the baseline and

implementation period included all reported incidents in the electronic reporting system for the inpatient adult units.

Stakeholders

To facilitate the practice change, stakeholders were involved in the project. The key stakeholders included clinical champions from frontline nursing staff, the chief nursing officer, the patient safety officer, the chief quality officer, the chief pharmacist, and the chief executive officer. All the stakeholders held a vested interest in improving the culture of safety.

Ethical Considerations

To assure anonymity of patients and staff involved in the project, all protected patient information (PPI) was removed so that those involved in peer review did not have access to PPI. Likewise, survey data obtained from staff were de-identified. Participants placed a tracking number (5 random digits) on their surveys to link pre- and post-surveys. Patients were not interviewed, nor were medical records reviewed or copied. Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act and privacy requirements per the California State University Long Beach Institutional Review Board (CSULB-IRB), University of Southern California Institutional Review Board (USC-IRB), and Los Angeles County + University of Southern California Medical Center were followed.

A permission letter signed by the chief nursing officer at the project facility was obtained to authorize the project and the use of nursing staff and necessary resources. If any issues had arisen from the project, the chief nursing officer or designee, USC-IRB, and CSULB-IRB would have been notified. The QI project was submitted to the USC-

IRB for review. Once approved, the USC-IRB approval letter was included with the application materials necessary for review and approval by the CSULB-IRB.

Measures

The project used outcome, process, and balancing measures as summarized in (Appendix D). Demographic information was collected to provide a description of the nurses participating in the pre- and post-AHRQ-SOPS™. The project used historical data and findings collected during the implementation to document the MI reporting rates at the project facility.

Patient Safety Culture

The adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ shown in Appendix A was used to measure the perceptions of safety culture (Burlison et al., 2016). The AHRQ-SOPS™ is in the public domain and may be used for clinical practice guidelines and QI without written permission.

There are 12 composite sections in the AHRQ-SOPS™ with nonpunitive response to error scoring the lowest at 37% (AHRQ, 2016). This project used eight items that made up three subscales (Management Support for Patient Safety, Feedback & Communication About Error, and Nonpunitive Response to Errors). Items from each subscale included “Hospital management provides a work climate that promotes patient safety,” “We are informed about errors that happen in this unit,” and “Staff feel like their mistakes are held against them.” The five-point Likert scale scored points 0 to 4 (strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 1, neither = 2, agree = 3, Strongly agree = 4). Items not answered were viewed as missing data and not included. The top-box scores total included the agree and strongly agrees points for positively worded items and disagree and strongly

disagree for negatively worded items. The negative-worded items were recoded to reflect a positive or negative response had the item been worded as a positive rather than a negative statement. Top-box scores were then divided by the total number of paired pre-post-surveys.

Medical Incidents

The second outcome measure was the count of MIs reported in the electronic reporting system for adult inpatient units. For purposes of this project, the operational definition of MIs included preventable errors, adverse events, sentinel events, and near misses.

System Factors

Individuals involved with the IBPR submitted their findings, including their *Ishikawa* diagrams, *5 Whys*, and/or other cause analysis paper and pencil form, after each peer review session. A list of eight common system findings were supplied to the IBPR participants. Examples of systems errors included issues related to equipment, procedures, and staffing (Appendix E). The systems errors were counted and tracked over the period of the project. Themes of errors were identified, condensed into a list, and reviewed with the chief quality and patient safety officer at regular intervals to ensure consistency in the evaluation process.

Perceptions of the Incident-Based Peer Review

A tool was developed to assess staff perceptions of the IBPR process. The tool was designed based on best practices identified in the literature as well as personal experiences with the assessment of staff perception. The tool included four items scored using a five-point Likert scale scoring points 0 to 4 (strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 1,

neither = 2, agree = 3, Strongly agree = 4). Items missing responses were not scored. Examples of the evaluative questions included in the tool were “The peer review meet expectations of a non-punitive response to an incident” and “I had adequate information to evaluate the incident.”

The top-box scores sample size which included the agree and strongly agrees responses were divided by the total sample size for analysis purposes with higher percentages reflecting better perceptions of the IBPR process. The clinical nursing director, patient safety officer, and chief quality officer assessed the tool for face validity.

Call Light Response Time

A balancing measure was identified to assesses whether the peer review intervention would cause new problems (IHI n.d.b). Roberts and Cronin (2017) found that one of the barriers to IBPR is the nurses having time to participate while meeting patient needs during the nurse’s absence. The peer review meeting required the nurses to leave their unit for approximately an hour. The patient uses the call light to notify the nurse that assistance is needed. On the three project units, the RNs are responsible for answering the call lights. Call light response time data identified if coverage in the unit was adequate during the IBPR nurse’s absence. Data for call light response time (CLRT) were collected from the call light’s integrated database.

Procedures

The procedure for this project is described below. An algorithm was developed to show the peer review implementation steps (Appendix F).

1. Approval obtained from USC-IRB and CSULB-IRB.

2. Engaged the stakeholders, including administrators, clinical champions, and pharmacists in the development of the educational program, the IBPR process, and evaluation tools.
3. Explanation of the program presented to the three medical/surgical units RNs at staff meetings highlighting the organization's attempt to change the culture where nurses are fearful of reporting MIs and being blamed to one where system errors that lead to the mistake are initially investigated.
4. The author distributed paper and pencil adapted- SOPS™ to a convenience sample of staff nurses from three inpatient adult medical/surgical during work hours on both shifts. The target compliance for SOPS™ submissions was 40%. When 40% compliance was achieved, each unit received pizzas. The adapted SOPS™ included a space for nurses to record a random five-digit number so surveys were tracked pre and post intervention. Nurses were encouraged to deposit completed adapted- SOPS™ in a box labeled "Safety Culture." After submission of the adapted- SOPS™ the RN received a raffle ticket with tear-off for a drawing of a \$50.00 gift card. A staff member from the Nursing Quality Management department was present during submission of surveys and to hand out the raffle tickets.
5. The Nursing Clinical Council provided the project author on which MI for the IBPR team to review.
6. The IBPR team consisted of one RN from each of the three medical-surgical units chosen by the nurse manager and clinical nursing director based on staffing, experience, and availability. The IBPR team consisted of three nurses and one

alternative in case one of the three should be unable to attend. The break relief nurse covered the nurse's patients during the meeting to maintain the mandated nurse to patient ratios. Education for the peer review team took place the week prior to the peer review by the author or trained designee. Information was provided on the IBPR, SVS, and a culture of safety. In addition, the peer review team learned what special cause is and how to complete a RCA including cause analysis tools to discover special causes including the Ishikawa diagram and 5 *Whys* (Appendix G).

7. The peer review team identified contributing factors. Material for the IBPR process included a summary statement from the project author, a de-identified narrative from the electronic report, policies that pertained to the incident, and reference materials such as an Ishikawa diagram and 5 *Whys* for using in an RCA. The project author attended all meetings to assist the team by providing any policy requests and questions regarding the cause and effect tools but did not provide any assistance in the outcome of the meeting. Refreshments were provided during the meeting. Peer review meetings occurred weekly. The goal to have eight one-hour meetings during the project period was met. Meeting times were either from 0500 to 0600 or from 1000 to 1100. These times were the least disruptive for the staff.
8. After completion of the peer review, the team submitted the peer review findings form. In addition, an evaluation form regarding the peer review was completed by each team member. Both forms included no information about the participants.

9. If the findings of the peer review showed a system issue, the findings were disseminated to the stakeholder responsible for the issue for follow-up action. If the peer review did not find a system cause, the findings were forwarded to the nurse manager for normal follow-up.
10. Peer review cases were presented on an electronic form and sent to all nursing staff on a monthly basis so that they could see that the project facility was actively trying to improve the culture of reporting and so that the nurses could learn from the cases.
11. Once all peer review meetings were completed, an adapted- SOPS™ was provided to all the nurses of the three medical-surgical units with the paper surveys deposited in the post-survey box.
12. Data collection during the intervention was organized on an Excel form for data analysis.

Data Analysis

Measures of central tendency and dispersion describe baseline characteristics of the sample. Data were entered into SPSS Statistics for analysis. Measures, how data were collected, and how results were displayed are summarized in Appendix D.

Changes in top-box scores (agree and strongly agree for positive-worded items; disagree and strongly disagree for negative-worded items) for perceptions of a safety culture (AHRQ-SOPS™) were presented in bar charts. The four negative-worded items were recoded (strongly disagree = 0, disagree = 1, neither = 2, agree = 3, Strongly agree = 4). The MI rates were presented on a C-chart. Data were grouped by week. The count of system causes found in each peer review meeting were presented as a run chart.

Perceptions of the value of the IBPR process were presented in a run chart. The balancing measure used an \bar{X} -R chart to display the call light response times. The time measured included the meeting day with four months of historical data serving as a baseline.

RESULTS

An IBPR was implemented to improve the culture of safety and reporting of MIs. This section presents the findings of the authors' quality improvement project including the sample demographics, the outcome measures (the adapted-AHRQ-SOPS™ and number of MIs), the process measures (evaluation of the IBPR and number of system causes found during IBPR), and the balancing measure (CLRT).

Data were collected between September and December 2019. The pre-adapted-AHRQ-SOPS™ was distributed and voluntarily completed by 88 nurses working on the three adult medical/surgical units of interest. At the end of 8 weeks a post-adapted-AHRQ-SOPS™ was distributed and voluntarily completed by 121 nurses from the same three adult medical/surgical units. Of the pre- and post-adapted AHRQ™-SOPS responses the author was able to match 67 to the same nurse. Demographics showed that 79% were female, 35% were baccalaureate prepared, and 52.2% had = < 3 years' experience (Table 1).

Table 1

Demographics

<u>Variable</u>	<u>N (%)</u>
Gender	
Male	14 (20.9%)
Female	53 (79.1%)
Education	
Diploma/ADN	26 (38.8%)
Bachelors	35 (52.2%)
Masters	6 (9.0%)
Years as RN	
0-3	35 (52.2%)
4-6	9 (13.4%)
7-10	2 (3.0%)
>10	21(31.3%)

Note: ADN=Associate Degree, Nursing; RN=registered nurse

Adapted Patient Safety Survey

Results of the adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ are presented in Table 2. For the positive-worded items, the top-box scores included the agree and strongly agree responses. For the negative-worded item, the top-box scores included the recoded disagree and strongly disagree responses. Seven of the eight items demonstrated improvements in post-survey top-box scores after initiating IBPR (percentage point improvements ranged from 3.0% to 13.4%). The items with the greatest improvements were “We are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports” (pre 58.2%, post 71.6%) and “We are informed about errors that happen in this unit” (pre 65.7%, post 79.2%). The item with a decrease in score was “When an event is reported, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem” (pre 40.3%, post 37.3%). Thus, following the intervention, fewer nurses believed that they were being reported vs. the problem being reported”

Table 2

Perceptions of Culture of Safety

Positively worded items	Pre-Survey	Post-Survey
	# / %	# / %
	Agree and strongly agree	Agree and strongly agree
Hospital management provides a work climate that promotes patient safety.	54 / 80.6	58 / 86.6
We are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports.	39 / 58.2	48 / 71.6
We are informed about errors that happen in this unit.	44 / 65.7	53 / 79.2
In this unit, we discuss ways to prevent errors from happening again.	55 / 82.1	60 / 89.6
Negatively worded items	Pre-Survey	Post-Survey
	# / %	# / %
	Disagree and strongly disagree	Disagree and strongly disagree
Staff feel like their mistakes are held against them	21 / 31.3	29 / 43.3
When an event is reported, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem.	27 / 40.3	25 / 37.3
Staff worry that mistakes they make are kept in their personnel file.	13 / 19.4	15 / 22.4
Hospital management seems interested in patient safety only after an adverse event happens.	24 / 35.8	27 / 40.3

Medical Incident Reporting

Medical incident data are presented on a control chart (C-Chart, Figure 1). Using Montgomery Rules, the C-chart is in control with no variation noted (Associates in Process Improvement, 2007). In other words, the intervention did not result in a significant change in MI reporting. The results reflect normal week-to-week variations in

MI reporting. The mean weekly MI was 13.24 prior to the initiation of IBPR and decreased to 11.77 after IBPR implementation.

Figure 1. C-chart of electronic medical incident reporting for three nursing units.

Number of System Causes

The first process measure was to identify whether the staff members were able to find system causes during their meeting. In all but one of the peer meetings, RNs were able to find a system cause (Figure 3). A run chart was used to show the number of system causes found on a weekly basis. The run chart shows normal variation with no unusual trend or pattern caused by an intervening variable.

Figure 2. Run chart of system causes found during peer review meetings.

Peer Review Evaluation

Twenty-five nurses completed the IBPR evaluations for a 100% response rate (Table 3). Seven of the IBPR had three RNs attend, and one IBPR had four RNs attend.

Table 3

Percentage of Top-Box Scores from Incidence-Based Peer Review Evaluation

Variable	N=25 # / %
The peer review met expectations of a non-punitive response to an incident.	23 / 92%
I had adequate information to evaluate the incident.	22 / 88%
The tools (fishbone, 5 whys) were easy to use.	25 / 100%
If involved in an incident I would like the incident reviewed in a peer review.	24 / 96.0%

Note: This table shows the percentage of top-box scores (agree and strongly agree) in the incidence-based peer review evaluations.

Call Light Response Time

The CLRT is the time it takes a nurse to answer a patient's call light. An Xbar-R chart (Figure 3) showed no variation in the CLRT pre-IBPR to post-IBPR.

Figure 3. Xbar-R chart for the mean and range of call light response time for 3 medical-surgical units.

DISCUSSION

Findings from this project, although somewhat mixed, showed that implementation of an incident-based peer review (IBPR) process was associated with an overall improved culture of safety. In addition, the IBPR process was not associated with an increase in staff burden, as measured by call response time. However, in spite of these positive findings, medical incident (MI) reporting did not increase following implementation of the IBPR as was predicted. In spite of the lack of increase in MI reporting, nurses who participated in the IBPR process did identify at least one system cause for a MI in all meetings except for one.

Perceptions of the Culture of Safety

The adapted Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Survey on Patient Safety Culture™ (AHRQ-SOPS™) assessed staff's changes in perception related to a culture of safety following the IBPR process. A total of 67 nurses completed both the pre- and post-adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ and were included in the analysis. Seven of the eight AHRQ-SOPS™ items improved after IBPR. The item which did not show improvement was “When an event is reported, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem” (40.3% disagreed with this statement pre IBPR, versus 37.3% post IBPR). This downward trend represented a greater feeling of mistrust or lack of a just culture when a MI is reported. It is possible that the IBPR process sensitized the nurses to how the organization examines MI. Soydemir, Seren Intepeler, and Mert (2017) found that evaluation resulted in the individual, rather than the system, being blamed for the MI. To mitigate this perception, clinical champions and managers should examine how errors are

presented and discussed and search for innovative approaches to improve the entire IBPR process.

The items showing the most improvement on the adapted AHRQ-SOPSTM were related to communication (“We are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports” and “We are informed about errors that happen in this unit”). Both items improved 13.4% from baseline. Research has found that communication is important to improving the culture of safety (Burlison et al., 2016; Soydemir et al., 2017). Good communication encourages collaboration between management and staff and may improve MI reporting. Motivation and problem-solving skills of staff improve when management and staff work together. The IBPR process may improve communication through the sharing of information.

Medical Incident Reporting

MI reporting did not increase during the project as anticipated. This two-month project found that MI reporting declined after implementation of the IBPR (13.24 MI reported per week baseline versus 11.77 per week after IBPR initiated). This could be understood from a number of perspectives. MI reporting had been on a downward trend in the medical center over the last few years. Also, baseline data collection occurred during the -period when new medical residents and interns begin clinical practice at the project facility, thus potentially inflating the baseline MI numbers. The influx of new inexperienced residents and interns at the subject hospital may have contributed to an increased MI baseline. In addition, the two-month project may be an insufficient time to fully evaluate the effectiveness of IBPR. It may also be possible that nurses were more careful in their care due to being aware of the project.

Process Measures: Incident-Based Peer Review

The effectiveness of the IBPR process was measured by the nurse's evaluation of the IBPR meeting and a count of system causes contributing to the MI. Nurses evaluated the process of IBPR positively over 90% of the time on all items of the evaluation tool (Table 3). There were nine unique system causes identified throughout the IBPR process. The most frequent system cause identified was high acuity with poor staffing. One IBPR meeting found no system cause for the MI. Two system causes were eventually referred to the hospital's Nursing Professional Practice Committee for evaluation. One system cause was related to an issue in the electronic medical record system which allowed the nurse to order blood products through either an order or a task. The process was confusing and contributed to near-miss situations. Nurses could go to the blood bank and access blood without the formal order. The recommendation from the IBPR meeting was to provide staff with a revised workflow on administering blood.

The IBPR process required flexibility on the part of both the RNs participating as well as the author. Originally, nurses participating in the IBPR process were to meet with the author prior to the MI review to discuss the process and the tools. However, the shift work of the nurses required the author to meet with the nurses individually for the pre-meeting. One IBPR meeting required a backup RN after one of the participants declined to take part. Another meeting had four RNs instead of three after a RN requested to participate.

Several cause and effect tools were utilized in the IBPR process. The 5 *Whys* was the most-used cause and effect tool in the IBPR meeting. This tool asks the nurses to identify a *why* for the MI five times in order to facilitate identifying a system cause. The

substitution test which asks the RN what they would do in the same situation was another popular tool. One RN used all the tools to find a system cause. The *Ishikawa* diagram was the most complex tool which may have contributed to its low use; however, it was given a high satisfaction rating. Although completion of the IBPR tools and attendance at the meetings were potentially time consuming, patient needs, as measured by the call light response time (CLRT), was not negatively impacted.

Call Light Response Time

CLRT was monitored to assess the impact on the unit while the RNs were participating in the IBPR process. The author planned several approaches to mitigate the deleterious effects on time away from the unit for IBPR. Travel time to the IBPR process was optimized by having the participants meet in a central location. In addition, IBPR meetings were scheduled when the lunch relief RN was available. The author scheduled regular meetings with the unit managers to ensure staff availability for the IBPR meeting. The Xbar R charts reflects a stable call light response time for the three medical-surgical units during the IBPR intervention.

Limitations

The results of this project may help guide institutions striving to improve their culture of safety but should be considered cautiously. First, the project was implemented over an 8-week period, which may have been insufficient to alter the culture of safety at the institution. To ensure completion of the practice change, IBPR meetings occurred weekly. This allowed for only a week for the staff to become acquainted with the process and to evaluate the MI. Regardless of the compressed schedule, the nurses evaluated the

process positively, were able to identify system causes, and the adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ generally reflected improvements in the culture of safety.

Response bias may have influenced some of the scores in the adapted AHRQ-SOPS™ survey. Polit and Beck (2012) define response bias as a measurement error that occurs when research participants respond in a characteristic way such as scoring all 1s or all 4s on a survey. On the surveys, several nurses consistently recorded the same digit for all responses. This may explain why the four negative-worded items demonstrated a lower percentage point change compared to the positive-worded items. Possibly, the nurses completing this survey did not read the items carefully and recorded all their responses in the same way. Moors, Kieruj, and Vermunt (2014) suggest that Likert scales are especially susceptible to response bias. The survey was designed to mitigate response bias; however, this may not have occurred.

The author's presence may have influenced nurses' responses on the IBPR evaluation tool. The IBPR RNs may have been uncomfortable expressing their true thoughts about the process in the presence of the author. Polit and Beck (2012) define the Hawthorne effect as participants altering their responses due to being observed. In the future, clinical champions will run the IBRR eliminating the need for the author's presence and mitigating the potential for the Hawthorne effect.

The author matched nurse responses from the pre- post AHRQ-SOPS™ surveys by having the nurses record a five-digit code on an index card and their employee number on the other side. The author kept the cards separately from the surveys and distributed the cards prior to having the nurses complete the post survey. The author was able to match 67 pre-surveys to post-surveys. In reality, 88 nurses completed a pre-survey, and

121 completed a post-survey. However, the results reported in this paper only reflect those obtained from both the pre- and post-survey. The perceptions of nurses who were not matched are not reported here. A decision was made to examine the results on an individual level (thus, the need for matching) and not an organization level (the results could have been aggregated pre and aggregated post and compared).

Recommendations and Clinical Implications

This QI project assessed the influence of IBPR on a culture of safety. In the future, an IBPR committee will be administered by the RN line staff, as line staff who are leading the IBPR may experience greater commitment to the process (Korkis et al., 2019). This commitment may positively influence the culture of safety. The IBPR will expand to all nursing units in the future, including the intensive care units where the disproportionate number of MIs occur, providing a larger sample of MIs to investigate.

In addition, IBPR meetings will change from weekly to monthly. This will increase time available for the RNs to consider the cases and learn how to use the cause and effect tools. The monthly schedule will provide for greater flexibility in scheduling and the opportunity of choosing longer meeting times.

In the future, the author will encourage communication between the unit managers and the staff involved with IBPR. Efforts to improve communication between leadership and line-staff may influence MI and improve the safety culture (Burlison et al., 2016). By communicating together in a team-oriented culture, change becomes more effective than in a hierarchical culture (David, 2018).

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APPENDIX A

Framework

Model for Improvement

Figure 4. Model for Improvement of incident reporting by implementing a peer-review process (adapted from API, n.d.).

APPENDIX B

Pre-Post Adapted AHRQ Hospital Surveys On Patient Safety Culture

The AHRQ-SOPS™ survey evaluates the safety culture of an organization. The questions in this survey refer to the culture of reporting medical incidents,

1. Random 5-digit number _____
(to be used only for matching pre and post survey results)
2. Gender: Male _____ Female _____ Prefer not to state _____
3. How many years have you been a RN? 1 -3 ___ 4-6 ___ 7-10 ___ >10 _____
4. Highest level of education: ASN _____ BSN _____ MSN _____
5. Hospital management provides a work climate that promotes patient safety.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

6. Hospital management seems interested in patient safety only after an adverse event happens.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

7. We are given feedback about changes put into place based on event reports.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

8. We are informed about errors that happen in this unit.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

9. In this unit, we discuss ways to prevent errors from happening again.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

10. Staff feel like their mistakes are held against them.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

11. When an event is reported, it feels like the person is being written up, not the problem.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

12. Staff worry that mistakes they make are kept in their personnel file.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

Thank you for participating in this survey

Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality (2016). AHRQ hospital survey on patient safety culture: User's guide. [pdf]
<https://www.ahrq.gov/sites/default/files/wysiwyg/professionals/quality-patient-safety/patientsafetyculture/hospital/userguide/hospcult.pdf>

APPENDIX C

Peer Review Participation Evaluation

1. The peer review met expectations of a non-punitive response to an incident.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

2. I had adequate information to evaluate the incident.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

3. The tools (fishbone, 5 whys) were easy to use.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

4. If involved in an incident I would like the incident reviewed in a peer review.

Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither	Agree	Strongly Agree
0	1	2	3	4

5. Do you have any suggestions that could improve this peer review process

(Answer in the space below)

Thank you for participating in this peer review and evaluation

APPENDIX D

Measures

Table 4

Measures

Type	Measure	How collected	Subgrouping	Type of chart
Outcome 1	Perceptions of safe culture. % of change in overall scores	AHRQ-SOPST TM (appendix B).	Pre-post-survey	Bar chart
Outcome 2	MI Count	Electronic reporting system	Weekly	C chart after 12 data points collected
Process 1	System causes Count	Peer review meetings Findings from Peer Review (appendix E)	Weekly	Run chart
Process 2	Perceptions of IBPR experience. % of top-box responses for each item.	Peer Review Evaluation Survey (appendix F)	Weekly	Run chart
Balancing	IBPR effect on nurse call light response time. Minutes.	Call light response time from integrated database	Weekly	Xbar R chart

APPENDIX E

Suggestion List of System Causes

The attached list are suggestions of possible system causes to assist you as you review the medical incident with issues including but limited to:

- Policy (vagueness, inaccurate language)
- Procedure (steps in completing the task)
- Documentation (orders, medication record)
- Storage (Automated dispensing machine, refrigerator- storage, dispensing)
- Equipment (functionability, availability)
- Supplies (not available, wrong items)
- Staffing (sub-optimal staffing, acuity, fatigue, stress)
- Distractions/interruptions

APPENDIX F

Peer Review Flow Algorithm

Figure 5. Peer review flow algorithm.

APPENDIX G

Educational Session Objectives and Plan

Educational Session Objectives

By end of educational session, participant will be able to state:

1. What an IBPR is
2. How IBPR impacts a culture of safety
3. What second victim syndrome is
4. Why system causes are important
5. Two cause effect tools used to perform a root cause analysis
6. Three answers that a root cause analysis uncovers
7. The four major steps of a root cause analysis

Education Plan

1. Discuss difference between IBPR and peer evaluation
2. Define culture of safety
3. Discuss how IBPR can impact a culture of safety
4. Discuss second victim syndrome and how it relates to MI and culture of safety
5. Discuss what system causes are and why they are important
6. Examples of system causes
7. Discuss what a root cause analysis is and the benefit of using it
8. Discuss the steps to complete a root cause analysis
9. Introduce cause analysis tools
10. What to do if stuck
11. Demonstration of root cause analysis using examples like being late to work
12. Allow time for questions